

INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS AND DIPLOMATIC CONNECTION IN THE HISTORY OF EASTERN COUNTRIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993007>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 25-May 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 28-May 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 31-May 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Diplomacy, diplomatic relations, ancient writings, diplomatic experience.

ABSTRACT

The article gives precious information about the history of diplomacy in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan. Moreover, the first writings about diplomatic relations and international connection with foreign countries. In ancient sources of Central Asia like "Avesto", "Kutadgu bilik", "Siyosatnoma" and "Temur tuzuklari" are appreciated as a valuable source about the history of diplomacy in our motherland.

Diplomatic relations of Eastern nations, in particular Uzbek state have a long history. The ancient Turkish settlement in Movarounnahr and the people who lived there and nomadic peoples in this region have continued the traditions of diplomacy. It is true that it has weakened in some cases due to the influence of certain events and faced a whirlwind of failures at times. "Embassy relations" have been used to describe the diplomatic ties that rulers of nations that have existed and operated on Turkestan's borders have established since antiquity. This notion has been around for a while.

If we look at historical sources, diplomatic relations are not only the main principle of today's independent state administration of Uzbekistan, but diplomatic relations were the main focus of the state even during the time of the first states that ruled over the borders of our country: the Turkish Khanate, the Timurids and the Khans. was the focus area. The main reason for this is the strengthening of state independence, the security, stability and development of the country largely depends on the active foreign policy conducted with foreign countries. The location of our country on the Great Silk Road has been a favorable opportunity for it to form economic, political and cultural relations with foreign countries and conduct mutual diplomatic relations.

The first views and writings about the diplomatic relations of our people were written in the book "Avesta"¹, which is considered the holy book of fire worship religion, the masterpiece of world culture, the first written source of Uzbek statehood. From the information given in this book, we can see that the first forms of diplomatic relations were formed in those times.

In "Avesta" the original spiritual essence of issues of communication with other countries - concepts related to values such as Erk, mutual equality and patriotism have been

¹ <https://www.elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/referatlar-mustaqil-ish-kurs-ishi/item/13357-avesto-qadimgi-tariximizni-orginishda-noyob-manba>

expressed. For example, in the 14th prophecy of Yosin, the second book of the Avesta, which consists of Zoroastrian Letters, God says: "I like good intentions, good words and good intentions". "Going beyond one's word, staying true to it, strictly following contracts in trade, paying debts on time, being free from deception and betrayal" are interpreted as manifestations of faith. These positive traits are intended to contribute to peace and happiness in daily interactions, as well as in relationships with other people and nations.

The great Turkish masterpiece "Kutadgu bilik" (Knowledge that leads to happiness) which is similar to the distinctive and universal values, contains an extensive description of our diplomatic principles. The 11th century, at the height of the Karakhanid kingdom, saw the creation of this work. There are opinions on diplomacy in "Qutadgu Bilik" that are all of incomparable importance, not only for their respective eras but also for current practice. This is evidence that the history of Turkish (Uzbek) diplomacy continued continuously as a part of our nation-state history and was enriched over centuries.

Another historical work written about state administration, diplomatic and political relations, leader's qualities and tasks is the work "Siyosatnoma"² (Politics) written in the 11th century. This work was written by Nizamulmulk, and the work contains valuable information about the description of the methods and secrets of State management. This work is dedicated to the rule of the Seljuks, one of the powerful states that operated in Central Asia in the early Middle Ages.

The author concluded the chapter of the work "Siyosatnoma" devoted to the issues of the Embassy with the following thoughts: "The ambassador is a person who reflects the character and intelligence of the ruler". It means that ambassador should behave appropriately, intelligently as he is the symbol of the country.

In the history of Uzbek statehood, Amir Temur's political management system, the reputation of his state, how knowledgeable and politically aware Amir Temur is, and his experience in establishing diplomatic relations deserve special recognition.

Amir Temur was the founder of a dynasty that was considered one of the most powerful states of his time. In addition, he was a patron of science and culture in his country, he became famous ruler who had a decisive influence on the historical changes that took place in Europe and Asia during his reign. Along with being a just ruler, he was also a skilled diplomat who made an incomparable contribution to the development of world civilization. Amir Temur's foreign policy was considered notable for its correspondence with the rulers of foreign countries, the fact that the etiquette of eastern diplomacy was evident in his diplomatic letters, the coldness between the countries, and his desire to solve problems peacefully. That is why the diplomacy of the Timurid era was considered the brightest example of international relations in the past.

Almost six centuries ago, Amir Temur, based on his skillful head of state and diplomatic experience, he expressed the opinion that the country's prospects cannot be achieved without establishing foreign relations with foreign countries. The correspondence and diplomatic relations of our great grandfather with the rulers of different countries, such as England, France, Ottoman Turks, Spain, China, and India, are a clear confirmation of his successful diplomatic policy.

² <https://n.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/yangi-kitoblar/nizomulmulk-siyosatnoma-siyar-ul-muluk>

In order to learn more about Amir Temur's state management and success in the diplomatic field, the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech dedicated to the activities of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and embassies abroad on January 11, 2018, he expressed his opinion: "There is a lot of information about the skillful diplomats and ambassadors in ancient history of our country. But their lives and activities, unfortunately, have not been studied in depth and comprehensively so far. If the Ministry of Foreign Affairs pays attention to this and publishes a separate book about the historical roots of diplomatic issues, the formation processes of Uzbek diplomacy during the period of Amir Temur, it would be an important guide for the employees of this field, first of all, for young diplomats.

As many historians and political scientists mentioned, Amir Temur left a deep mark in history as the most skilled diplomat of his period. The great commander and ruler Amir Temur, as a great statesman, skillfully used the peaceful way of diplomacy and military measures to achieve his goals with his intelligence.

One of the unique aspects of Amir Temur's diplomacy is that he followed the etiquette of Eastern diplomacy in all his appeals, even in his letters written in the form of strict demands. It is not difficult to learn from the historical letters inherited from those times that Sahibqiran always responded with culture and decency to the names of the rulers of some countries, which were written in a rude form, and in some cases with anger and ignorance. This is clearly confirmed by Amir Temur's letter to the French king Charles VI with the words "Greetings and I declare peace!" (Salom va tinchlik e'lon qilaman!)³

The state policy, diplomatic relations conducted by the great leader Amir Temur, as well as the important areas of state administration such the socio-political and spiritual-ideological environment of the state, interest in religion and science, have been studied with great interest by world scientists.

As a result of the research conducted by the French orientologists in the process of studying the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period, we must emphasize that they thoroughly studied the management and military system, diplomacy, culture, religion, philosophy and scientific thinking, art and architecture of that time.

One of the French orientologists, Professor L. Keren, carefully studied the Eastern and Western sources on this subject before writing a work on Amir Temur and the Timurid dynasty. Professor investigated the works of Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi and Ibn Arabshah chronicles, "Diaries" of Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, and many historical archival documents and written sources.

Professor L. Keren is the author of a number of works and articles devoted to Amir Temur and his relations with Europe. One of his most important books "The reign of Temur or Sahibkiran" (Temur yoxud Sohibqiron saltanati) was first published in 1978. Another of his major works, the book "The Samarkand Road in the Time of Timur" (Temur davrida

³ <https://xs.uz/uz/post/frantsuz-olimi-amir-temurning-siyosij-zakovatiga-diplomatik-mahorati-va-bunyodkorligiga-tan-bergan>

Samarqand yo'li) (Paris, 1990), was prepared as part of the UNESCO "Silk Road - Road of Communication" program⁴.

Without any hesitation, one can say that Lucien Keren was listed among the famous scholars who researched on Timurid dynasty because of these books. Particularly, describing Sohirqiran's personality, emphasizing him as a successful general, a talented diplomat, and a supporter of science in Europe was the great deal of the professor.

Among the historical books about the diplomacy of our country, we can cite as an example books such as "Boburnoma", "The history of Rashidi" (Tarixi Rashidi), "Khumayunnama" (Xumoyunnoma) written by kings and khans. However, it is also worth noting that "Tuzuki Temuri" himself has in many respects the methods of governing the state, the criteria for relations with friends and enemies, which are described in ancient Turkish texts, for example, in "Qutadgu Bilik", it is noticeable that opinions such as the need to act based on rational virtues are relied on and they have been further improved. So, the issues reflected in the ancient writings related to the sphere of our statehood have become more refined over the centuries, they have been developed in accordance with certain conditions and requirements of the time.

Another masterpiece created in this field is the work "Dastur-ul-muluk"⁵ written by Khoja Samandar Termizi. The book is dedicated to the administration of the 17th century ruler of Bukhara, Subkhanquli Muhammad Bahadir Khan, and his diplomatic relations (1645-1680). The book is called "Dastur-ul Muluk" (Guide to Kings) by author. The author paid special attention to embassy issues in this work. The author was engaged in diplomatic practice at the same time as writing down historical events. Khoja Samandar emphasizes the enormous, in some cases, decisive importance of the embassy in the improvement of foreign relations and the level of relations with other countries.

Briefly say, the book "Dastur-ul Muluk" describes the aspects that should be given great attention by the ruler and the ambassador in the process of diplomatic relations with foreign countries, the characteristics of the ambassador, mistakes that can be made in the process of diplomatic relations, and a number of important aspects of diplomacy.

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that if one pay attention the history of diplomacy of Uzbekistan, we can see that the first writings about diplomatic relations are contained in the "Avesta" book of the Zoroastrian religion. The researches carried out by historians in later periods were also reflected in the works "Qutadgu Bilik", "Temur Tuzuklari", "Siyosatnoma", "Dastur-ul Muluk" which are considered masterpieces of the Turkic peoples.

In addition, it is clear how important the international relations conducted by the Turkish ruler with foreign countries, especially the works which are written about the Temiry dynasty, founded by our great grandfather Amir Temur.

It is especially important that the information about the governing system, socio-political, spiritual-cultural, and diplomatic spheres of the state carried out by Amir Temur was studied with great interest by political scientists and historians from all over the world.

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⁴ <https://xs.uz/uz/post/frantsuz-olimi-amir-temurning-siyosij-zakovatiga-diplomatik-mahorati-va-bunyodkorligiga-tan-bergan>

⁵ <https://www.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/jahon-she-riyati/fors-tojik-she-riyati/xoja-samandar-termiziy>

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